

AYURVEDA PERSPECTIVE OF RASAMANIKYA AND ITS ROLE IN SKIN DISORDERS: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT -, Rasamanikya is a medicine widely used in Ayurvedic practice for various treatments. Rasamanikya was created by Shuddha Haratala and named as Rasamanikya because of Manikya (ruby) color of milk. Rasamanikya can be prepared by classical Abhraka Patra method and Sharava Samputa method etc. Due to its Ayurvedic properties and health benefits, classical definition of Rasamanikya puts it as a treatment for skin diseases. Therefore, this article examines the Ayurvedic perspective of Rasamanikya and its role in skin diseases.

Keywords - Ayurveda, Rasamanikya, skin, disorders, Kustha Roga

INTRODCUTION

The revolution in Ayurveda technology brings consider of global populace toward this classical technology of healing and fitness management. The scientific, proof primarily based and rational strategies of Ayurveda make it choice of remedy for lots human being. Ayurvda described numerous standards and treatment plans for the remedy of diseases consisting of use of herbal herbs and classical Ayurveda method.

RasManikya is one such Ayurveda formulation mentioned in classical literary of Ayurveda that offers beneficial in lots of

skin issues and different fitness problems. RasManikya is prepared by heating Shuddha Haratala powder that's sandwiched among Abharaka Patra. It have to use best after endorse by means of clinical practitioner on the grounds that over-dosage can also cause toxic impact, not encouraged in being pregnant and at some stage in length of lactation. It must be avoid the usage of RasManikya in youngsters.

**THE MAJOR CONSTITUENTS OF
RASMANIKYA ARE AS FOLLOWS**

1. Shuddha Haratala (Arsenic tri-sulphide)
2. Shuddha Gandhaka (Purified sulphur)
3. Manashila (Arsenic di-sulphide)
4. Shuddha Parada (Purified mercury)
5. Naga Bhasma (Lead calx)
6. Tamra Bhasma (Copper in micronized formulation)
7. Abhraka Bhasma (Processed Mica)
8. Loha Bhasma (Iron Bhasma)
9. Vataksheera (Ficus bengalensis)
10. Nimba (Azadirachta indica)
11. Guduchi (Indian Tinospora)
12. Hrivera (Pavonia odorata)
13. Tala (Borassus flabellifer)
14. Vanari (Atmagupta)
15. Shobhanjana (seeds of Moringa oleifera)
16. Nirgundi (Vitex negundo)

COMMON HEALTH BENEFITS OF RASMANIKYA:

it's far used for anemia, fever, pruritis, hiccups and jaundice. It allows in sicknesses that arise because of the vitiation of Vata and Kapha, offers fitness advantages in skin and respiratory diseases. It also relieves signs and symptoms of Vatarakta, Arshas and Nadi Vrana, and many others.

RASMANIKYA IN SKIN DISORDERS

It offers beneficial outcomes inside the management of illnesses which include; leprosy, surface wounds, pus, boils dryness of skin, eczema, rashes and leukoderma, and many others. Impurity of blood is one of the purpose of skin illnesses and Rasmanikya acts as Raktashodhak means it purify blood accordingly gives relief from pores and skin issues, it is believed that presence of purified sulfur enables to detoxify blood. The components of Rasmanikya acts as Kushtha har thus relive signs of leprosy or many other pores and skin sicknesses. The formulations imparts calming and soothing outcomes hence assist to reduces ache, itching and burning sensation associated with skin troubles. It reduces damage caused by sun-burn, repair energies and redress blood morbidity. The immunosuppressants results supply advantages in autoimmune skin diseases together with; Polymorphous light Eruption and Systemic Lupus Erythematosus, etc. The presence of metal compounds initiates re-pigmentation misplaced with the aid of ailment outcomes. The substances of formula assist to manage Kapala and Audumbera Kushtha as a result improves manifestations of erythroderma.

BIOLOGICAL RESPONSE OF RASMANIKYA IN SKIN DISORDERS

- a. It balances Vata and Kapha thus relieve skin illnesses.
- b. It relief fever related to different diseases.
- c. dispose of immoderate phlegm and pollutants from frame which may also on occasion initiate pathogenesis of skin sicknesses.
- d. It treats ailment like; ring computer virus, scabies, psoriasis and urticaria, and so forth.
- e. Rasamanikya breaks immunological adversity which can trigger pores and skin manifestation.
- f. Relieve ache, irritation and swelling
- g. The antimicrobial property resists skin infection
- h. The steel components complements color, complexion and integrity of pores and skin

The important substances of RasManikya are Tamara Bhasma, Hartala and Abhrak Bhasma. Tamara Bhasma facilitates in purple blood cells formation as a consequence restore complexion and shade of skin. The presence of Tamara Bhasma reduces possibilities of ailment that could get up because of the vitiation of blood. Hartala gives beneficial outcomes in skin

sicknesses like; itching, eczema and herpes, etc. Abhrak Bhasma any other factor of RasManikya boosts immunity accordingly prevent pores and skin contamination, it also imparts strength for this reason keep bodily compatibility and skin integrity. Formulations enables to keep youthfulness of skin nourishes pores and skin and rehydrate pores and skin consequently provide natural beauty and electricity of pores and skin. RasManikya prevent wrinkles and skin signs and symptoms of untimely aging.

EFFECT OF RASMANIKY ON DOSHAS FOR SKIN VITALITY

Ayurveda formula RasManiky offers useful outcomes closer to the pacification of Doshas and gives particular benefits within the management of skin troubles as depicted in parent 1.

- The pores and skin predominance to Vata Dosha continue to be dry and touchy to touching sensation, RasManikya pacifies extra Vata accordingly prevent skin dehydration and sensitivity.
- Pacification of Pitta Dosha by means of RasManikya facilitates in breakouts & photosensitivity tolerance of skin.

- RasManikya correct aggravated Kapha dosha for that reason assist to keep pores and skin texture and tolerant to sun exposure.
- The simultaneous corrections of Vata-Pitta related to skin troubles facilitates in dry and sensitive pores and skin.
- The ingredients of formula pacifies Kapha-Pitta collectively therefore withstand skin troubles that can arise because of the immoderate oily layer.
- It removes Ama (toxins) collected under the pores and skin.
- Improves circulate accordingly complements deliver to pores and skin tissue.
- Elements of RasManikya beautify digestive hearth therefore contributes toward improvement of skin tissue.

Figure 1: Effects of RasManiky on skin health through Doshas balances

S. No.	Effects on of RasManiky	Health benefits to skin tissue
1	Establish balances of <i>Vata</i>	Decrease skin susceptibility to become thin and dry. Resist formation of wrinkle.
2	Establish balances of <i>Pitta</i>	Decrease skin susceptibility to rashes and breakouts.
3	Establish balances of <i>Kapha</i>	Balances oily skin, remove blackheads, pimples and help to prevent prevalence of disease like; eczema.

CONCLUSION

Rasamanikya is Ayurveda drug own Manikya (Ruby) colour, encouraged for the management of Shwasa, Phirana Roga, Vicharchika, Bhaganadara, Vatarakta and Kustha Roga, etc. The Ayurveda residences of Rasamanikya helps to prevent pores and skin associated health illnesses. It facilitates to treat many pores and skin problems like; leprosy, wounds & pus, dry pores and skin, rashes, leukoderma and eczema, etc. It purify blood (Raktashodhak), imparts

calming & soothing effects, reduces itching, save you sun-burn, imparts immunosuppressants outcomes, improves manifestations of erythroderma, repair complexion and shade of skin, boosts immunity, prevent pores and skin contamination, imparts energy & pores and skin integrity, hold youthfulness, nourishes & rehydrate pores and skin, prevent early wrinkles & signs of premature growing older and pacifies Doshas therefore facilitates in the control of several pores and skin issues.

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